

LIMITS OF SUPERSATURATION IN SOLUTIONS OF SOLID NON-ELECTROLYTES

BY A. C. CHATTERJI, A. N. BOSE, R. P. RASTOGI AND RAM GOPAL

Supersaturation of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been studied and it is shown that practical and theoretical limits are very much similar provided the effect of the internal pressures of the solvent and the solute is taken into consideration. It is pointed out that the limits of supersaturation cannot be predicted very accurately due to uncertainty in fixing up the exact values for ' r ' and σ .

It has been shown in a previous communication from this laboratory (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 145) that the equation of Jones and Partington (*Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 29, 35) namely,

$$T = T_s \left(1 - \frac{1M\sigma}{\rho\lambda r} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

which should be strictly applicable to non-dissociating solutes, can also be used for solutions of electrolytes. It is proposed to make an attempt in the present communication to study the application of equation (1) to solutions of non-electrolytes taking into account the recent important advances in the solubility theory with special reference to the concept of internal pressures of the solvent and solute. As the method of attacking the problem is very much similar to that used in the paper cited above, most of the steps which would have involved mere repetition, are omitted here.

Solubilities S_r and S_∞ of particles of radii ' r ' and ∞ are given by Ostwald-Freundlich equation viz.,

$$\frac{RT}{M} \ln \frac{S_r}{S_\infty} = \frac{2\sigma}{\rho r}$$

whence one gets

$$\ln S_r = \frac{2\sigma M}{\rho r RT} + \ln S_\infty \quad \dots (2)$$

Solubilities of non-electrolytes in different solvents have been studied widely, specially during recent years both from the theoretical and practical standpoint by Hildebrand and his collaborators, Mortimer, Scatchard, Kendall and others (cf "Recent Advances in General Chemistry", Glasstone, 1936, p. 229 *et. seq.*). For ideal system $\ln S_\infty$ can be expressed as a function of temperature in the following relationship :

$$\ln S_\infty = \frac{L_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

where L_r is the latent heat of fusion and T_m , the melting point of the solute. L in ideal cases is equal to the heat of solution and is independent of the solvent. Since we have to deal mostly with non-ideal systems, the empirically modified form of (2), as proposed by Mortimer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1416; 1923, 45, 633) who takes into

account the effect of the internal pressures of both the solvent and solute, should be considered. The equation of Mortimer is

$$\ln S_{\infty} = \frac{fL_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right)$$

where f denotes the effect due to differences in internal pressures. If π_1 and π_2 are the relative internal pressures of the two components with respect to naphthalene as unity, then according to Mortimer*

$$(i) \quad f = \pi_1 - \pi_2 + 1, \text{ if } \pi_1 > \pi_2 > 1,$$

$$(ii) \quad f = \pi_1 - \frac{1}{\pi_2} + 1, \text{ if } \pi_1 > 1 > \pi_2,$$

$$(iii) \quad f = \frac{1}{\pi_1} - \frac{1}{\pi_2} + 1, \text{ if } \pi_1 \text{ and } \pi_2 \text{ are less than } 1.$$

Substituting $\frac{fL_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right)$ for $\ln S_{\infty}$ in (2) one gets at T

$$\ln S_r = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + \frac{fL_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right)$$

$$\text{i.e. } S_r(T) = \text{Exp.} \left[\frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + \frac{fL_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

and at $(T + \delta T)$

$$S_r(T + \delta T) = \text{Exp.} \left[\frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{(\rho + \delta\rho)(r + \delta r)(T + \delta T)R} + \frac{fL_r}{RT_m} - \frac{fL_r}{R(T + \delta T)} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{But } S_r(T) = S_r(T + \delta T)$$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + \frac{fL_r}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right) = \frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{R(\rho + \delta\rho)(r + \delta r)(T + \delta T)} + \frac{fL_r}{RT_m} - \frac{fL_r}{R(T + \delta T)}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r T} - \frac{fL_r}{T} = \frac{2M(\sigma + \delta\sigma)}{(T + \delta T)(r + \delta r)(\rho + \delta\rho)} - \frac{fL_r}{(T + \delta T)} \quad \dots (6)$$

Thus, it is clear that all terms involving T_m vanish and (6) is exactly the same as (8) of the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) except that λ has been replaced by fL_r . A further simplification of (6) and neglecting of infinitesimals of higher order than one and, finally, integration leads to

$$T = C \left(1 - \frac{2M\sigma}{fL_r \rho r} \right) \quad \dots (7)$$

The relationship between π_1 and π_2 has not been clearly defined by Mortimer as an interchanging of their places would yield different results. A more rational approach to define the relationship between π_1 and π_2 , which was probably intended by Mortimer, is that π_1 and π_2 are so arranged that the first two terms i.e. $P(\pi_1)$ and $Q(\pi_2)$ give a positive value, in other words $P(\pi_1) - Q(\pi_2)$ is always positive, $P(\pi_1)$ and $Q(\pi_2)$ being functions of π_1 and π_2 .

When $T = T_s$, $r = \infty$ and then $C = T_s$ which when combined with (7) yields

$$T_s - T = \frac{2M\sigma}{f\rho r L_v} T_s. \quad \dots (8)$$

It may be noticed that in (8), f occurs in the denominator of the r. h. s. expression. This reduces the work term $2M\sigma/\rho r$ to $2M\sigma/\rho r f$ and, therefore supersaturation will tend to be smaller, the larger the factor ' f '. In other words, it means that the effect of a large difference in the internal pressures of the solute and solvent is that there is a greater tendency of the solute being thrown out of the solution and a smaller amount of work barrier is to be surmounted, that is to say, a smaller amount of work is necessary to be performed for the formation of the stable crystal nucleus of radius ' r ' than would have been the case otherwise, *i. e.* when there is no difference in the internal pressures of the two components. It has been shown in earlier papers that ' r ' is of the order of 10^{-6} cm. Using $r = 1 \times 10^{-6}$ cm. the values of $T_s - T$ have been calculated in different systems. The values of f utilised here are those given by Mortimer (*loc cit.*).

TABLE I

Solvent.	Solute.	f .	σ .	L_v .	$(T_s - T)_{obs}$	$(T_s - T)_{calc.}$
1. Naphthalene	Aniline	1.46	40	4557.0	9.0	9.6
2. "	Methyl alcohol	3.35	40	"	4.5	4.2
3. "	Ethyl alcohol	2.90	40	"	4.8	6.5
4. "	Acetic acid	1.95	40	"	6.0	7.0
5. "	Nitrobenzene	1.07	40	"	8.0	12.9
6. "	Benzene	1.07	40	"	5.0	12.9
7. "	Toluene	1.07	40	"	6.0	12.9
8. "	Chlorobenzene	1.06	40	"	4.0	12.8
9. "	Hexane	1.8	40	"	8.0	7.7
10. "	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	1.01	40	"	13.7	13.5
11. "	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	1.18	40	"	8.0	11.0
12. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	Benzene	1.01	40	3346.0	15.0	12.5
13. "	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	1.02	40	"	10.0	11.0
14. "	Bromobenzene	1.01	40	"	9.0	20.0
15. <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	Bromobenzene	1.01	52	3998.0	10.5	8.3
16. "	Benzene	1.01	52	"	23.0	20.0
17. Anthracene	Benzene	1.00	40	6639.0	8.0	12.0
18. Benzoic acid	Benzene	1.31	40	4123.0	8.0	10.4
19. "	Acetone	1.06	40	"	13.0	12.8
20. "	Toluene	1.30	40	"	19.0	10.4

Table I bears out the fact that the correspondence between the calculated and observed values of $T_s - T$ is not very good. However, similarity between the two sets of values is very well marked. There are two main factors which probably vitiate the

results. Firstly, the exact value of ' r ' is very difficult to fix as 1×10^{-6} cm. is, at the most, a very rough approximation and it may actually vary from 1 to 9×10^{-6} cm.; secondly, the values of σ are also highly approximate. Factors like association and compound formation may also play a significant role in controlling supersaturation. Consequently, one should not expect an accurate correspondence between the calculated and observed values.

Incidentally the results give a very interesting support to the previous conclusions that ' r ' is of the order of 1×10^{-6} cm. A higher value e. g. 10^{-5} cm. would yield a very small, and in fact, negligible supersaturation and the value of σ , which is the only other uncertain quantity in the equation (8), cannot be of the order of 300 or 3000 ergs., which could counterbalance a larger ' r '. From the various sources it appears that the ' σ ' for organic solutes is in general, less than 50 ergs. It appears therefore fairly established that ' r ' is of the order of 10^{-6} cms.

One of us (A. N. B.) is thankful to the Scientific Research Committee, United Provinces, and the other (R. P. R.) to the Lucknow University, for granting a research fellowship.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received January 10, 1949